

Biodiversity and Ecology of Freshwater Pools on the Rocky Outcrops of Peninsular India

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Rocky outcrops are areas of exposed rock, distinct from the surrounding landscape. Typically, they are devoid of, or have a very thin layer of soil, often leading to a lack of permanent woody vegetation cover. These unique, harsh and often desolate landscapes have attracted the interest of ecologists for decades. However, rocky outcrops in India and south Asia are yet unexplored compared to those in Australia, parts of Africa and the Americas. Peninsular India has a long, complex tectonic history, varied climate and topography, and supports tremendous biodiversity, including the Western Ghats global biodiversity hotspot. The diverse landforms in this region have rocky outcrops of different geological formations, including extensive flat plateaus, monolithic inselbergs (a single rock emerging from the landscape) or patches of boulders (Fig. 1). The geological origins of these outcrops also vary, ranging from the ancient granites (~2 billion years old) to relatively younger basalts and laterites (~65 million years old). Although they seem barren and lifeless, especially in the dry phase, rocky outcrops support a rich and unique biota. These outcrops are climatically distinct from the surrounding landscape, making them ecologically unique. Moreover, these ancient rocks also have long cultural associations with humans, as observed through prehistoric art (e.g., petroglyphs ~ >10 000 years old), religious significance and important roles in defense (e.g., forts) (Fig. 2).

Rock pools are interesting habitats on these outcrops, formed when shallow depressions in the rock are inundated by precipitation. These pools have clear boundaries and are patchily distributed in the rock matrix, and hence are thought to resemble “islands”. Hence, pools are isolated or occur in clusters on the outcrops, with a wide variation in the distance between adjacent pools. Due to their shallow depth and the physical properties of the rock (e.g., heating), the pools typically hold water for short periods of time, ranging from a few days to a few months, after which the pools dry up, only to fill again in the next precipitation cycle (hydroperiod). Rock pools on the same outcrop can also vary greatly in features like depth, surface area etc., which can also affect their

hydroperiod (Fig. 3).

Despite their short hydroperiod and usually small size, rock pools are rich in aquatic biodiversity, ranging from microscopic phytoplankton and zooplankton to larger algae, macrophytes, insects and vertebrates. The biodiversity of these fascinating habitats has not been well explored in south Asia, and especially in biodiverse regions like India. Hence, recent studies on these habitats have led to the discovery of hitherto undescribed species belonging to several taxa. Most of these species are endemic to these habitats, often occurring only in a few pools. Identifying and documenting this unknown biodiversity is thus very important to gain a deeper understanding about these habitats and promote their conservation, and this has been an important part of my research (Kulkarni & Pai, 2016). A big part of this work involves finding and sampling rocky outcrops, most of which are remote. They are also quite difficult to access, particularly during the monsoons as climbing wet rock is quite literally treading a very slippery slope! The samples collected from the pools are then examined microscopically in the lab, and a combination of morpho-taxonomic and molecular phylogenetic methods are used to identify species. This ongoing collaborative work has resulted in the discovery of new species of copepods and large branchiopods, some of which have been formally named (Kulkarni *et al.*, 2018; Padhye *et al.*, 2018, 2023; Kulkarni *et al.*, in prep.).

Studying the ecology of these pools is the next important step. The landscape is strongly influenced by the seasonal availability of water. For the pools too, the duration of inundation and the frequency of these wet-dry cycles (collectively termed the hydroregime) is a key driver. Arthropods, represented mainly by insects and crustaceans are a major component of the faunal diversity of rock pools. They often exhibit characteristic adaptations to survive the dynamic environment of the pools, particularly the dry phase. Some of these adaptations include short life cycles (as short as a few days), production of desiccation-resistant “eggs” (or cysts) and variable patterns of hatching of these cysts. The arthropod community comprises both active (insects) and passive (crustaceans) dispersers, where the former can move between pools on their own, while the latter require help from certain vectors (wind, water currents, animals) to disperse to other pools. The passive dispersers are also “resident” taxa, as they hatch from the resting eggs in the sediment after inundation (*i.e.*, populate the pool from within), while the active dispersers colonize pools from outside. These broad categories also relate to the ecological preferences of these organisms, with

Fig. 1 Different rocky outcrops in peninsular India. Note the near absence of vegetation cover. A - Rocky outcrops in the peninsular Indian landscape, B - Granite monolith at Savandurga, a fort, C - Basaltic plateaus in the northern Western Ghats (note the characteristic horizontal bands of the Deccan Trap formation), D - A lateritic plateau at the crestline of the northern Western Ghats, E - The top of the granite monolith at Bhongir. (Photos by Mihir Kulkarni)

Fig. 2 Historical and cultural significance of rocky outcrops. A – Prehistoric (~10 000 year old) petroglyph on a laterite outcrop in Maharashtra, B – Sculptures at an historic Jain site near Madurai (~ 2 000 year old), C – The boulder strewn landscape at the historic city of Hampi (~ 12 AD), D - Fortified top of the basalt outcrop at Visapur. (Photo A by Sudhir Risbud, Wikimedia commons; Photos B-D by Mihir Kulkarni)

the colonizing active dispersers being more selective (specialists) than the resident passive dispersers (generalists). Variations in the rock pool environment and the arrangement of the pools in space (distance between pools) are thus important drivers of these communities, especially as they can affect active and passive dispersers differently.

To better understand the ecology of arthropod communities in these rock pools, I monitored communities in selected pools on one outcrop over their entire hydroperiod. In this study (Kulkarni *et al.*, 2019), we observed that the number of arthropod species in these rock pools was positively associated with the hydroperiod of the pools. Hydroperiod was also the main environmental driver of the composition of these communities – pools with similar hydroperiod had similar communities. We also observed that spatial factors (distance between pools) influence the pair-wise differences in communities of pools. However, this varied among different groups of passive dispersers, possibly related to the differences in their dispersal capacities.

The role of the environment in shaping communities was observed, but environmental factors themselves can act at different spatial scales. For example, pool depth and annual precipitation both influence hydroperiod, but they act at small spatial scale (few meters) and larger spatial scale (few hundred kilometres) respectively, to shape communities in the pools. The species in these communities have different functional traits (*e.g.*, dispersal mode, body size), which shape their responses to environmental factors, *e.g.*, species with better dispersal abilities can disperse to farther habitats relative to poor dispersers. As functional traits are fundamental ecological attributes of species, they are strongly shaped by the species' evolutionary relationships. Thus, closely related species often have similar functional traits, which in turn drives the similarities in their responses to environmental factors. Such functional similarity can drive species interactions, where species with similar functional traits can compete for resources. This is especially important in habitats like rock pools, which have

limited resources, but also support high species diversity.

To investigate the roles of these processes in rock pools, we used a larger dataset (32 pools on 3 outcrops), where the communities were sampled over the entire hydroperiod (2-7 months) of the pools (Kulkarni *et al.*, 2023). We identified 68 species of arthropods in these pools, with up to 30 and 34 species in individual pools and outcrops, respectively. Although we did not identify several taxa like cyclopoid copepods, dipterans, turbellarians, rotifers etc., the observed diversity is comparable to that of extensively studied sites, *e.g.*, Australia. These diverse communities were largely shaped by environmental factors acting at small spatial scales, with substantial inter-species variation. Among these factors, hydroperiod was again the key driver for both active and passive dispersers. However, the influence of spatial factors was stronger for passive dispersers, indicating a potential role of dispersal limitation in shaping passive disperser communities, but this will need additional investigation. We also found a strong influence of phylogenetic relationships and functional traits in shaping species responses, where different functional traits were involved in species' response to environmental factors acting at different spatial scale. Thus, species' evolutionary history plays an important role in communities, reflecting the selection pressure of the environment. Interestingly, we did not detect many putative species associations in these communities, reinforcing the influence of the pool environment, rather than species interactions, in shaping communities in these habitats (Kulkarni *et al.*, 2023).

The importance of the evolutionary history of species brings attention to the evolutionary significance of the outcrops themselves. The long, complex tectonic and bioclimatic history of peninsular India has driven the evolution of the extant biota, which is a mixture of ancient Gondwanan, Eurasian, Palearctic and endemic Indian lineages. The distribution of these lineages in the landscape provides clues about the biogeography of these organisms. In some ongoing work (Kulkarni *et al.*, in

Fig. 3 Rock pools on granite (A, D, E), laterite (B, C, G) and basalt (F) outcrops. (Photos by Mihir Kulkarni)

prep), I analyzed the taxonomic and phylogenetic diversity of geologically different outcrops (granite, basalt, laterite) in India. While taxonomic diversity focuses on species identities, phylogenetic diversity considers their evolutionary history. Thus, a site with higher phylogenetic diversity indicates the presence of evolutionarily older/different lineages, highlighting their value for conservation prioritization. My preliminary observations indicate that rocky outcrops generally have a higher evolutionary diversity than “non-outcrop” habitats. Different outcrops also vary in species composition and phylogenetic diversity, where granite and laterite outcrops have high scores. Furthermore, the current distribution of ancient Gondwanan and Indian endemic lineages is mostly restricted to granite and laterite outcrops. This underscores their value for conservation, which is very much needed for these landscapes.

Rocky outcrops in India are often considered “barren wastelands”, which greatly undermines their importance as reserves of rich biodiversity. These landscapes are also associated with ecosystem services (provisioning, cultural, recreational), which are important for sustaining small, traditional settlements in the vast rocky expanse. However, these outcrops are increasingly being threatened by activities like mining, changes in land use and pollution, and the looming challenge of climate change. Through these studies, I hope to contribute to scientific as well as public knowledge about these unique habitats and their contribution to the ecological, historical and cultural heritage of India.

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